

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL LEADERSHIP BUSINESS MODELS IN GLOBAL MARKETS

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Abstract

The article discusses aspects of the implementation of technological leadership business models in the context of companies digital transformation. The difference between the technological leadership business model and the traditional business model with the definition of the architecture of the business model of 4 links (technological, social, financial and responsibility) is established. It is proved that the implementation of the technological leadership business model is optimal for the formation of competitive advantages of the company in global markets. The reported study was funded by RSF (Russian Science Foundation), project number №23-28-01233, <https://rscf.ru/en/project/23-28-01233/>.

Keywords: technological leadership, business model, digital technologies, global market, competition, ecosystem, digital responsibility.

The modern economy is absolutely dependent on digital technologies and how they are incorporated into the functioning of companies, interaction with suppliers and customers. These processes are not something unique, because technologies have always had and continue to have an impact on production, services and business in general, but now companies are increasingly focused on achieving technological leadership in the markets. Such technological leadership does not just become one of the elements of the company's competitive advantages, but becomes the basis for the stability of competitive advantages in conditions of turbulence [1] and creates a prolonged position in business, unlike classical dominance in the markets due to the company innovative activity.

The digital economy has also absolutely expanded the boundaries of doing business, so technological leadership is most relevant for analysis in the aspect of global markets [2]. In addition, with the spread of artificial intelligence, there is a need to study the phenomenon of digital leadership [3]. Now there is a wide spread of technologies and technical achievements in the Industry 4.0 context, and companies in various industries and services in their activities are focused on active implementation in order to increase labor productivity and resource efficiency, as well as gain advantages over competitors based on knowledge of individual customer needs [4]. Digital transformation has actually reconfigured the boundaries of each individual company, made the company's products open to consumers as a community within the framework of joint consumption. It is a motive for companies specializing in new technologies or use to move to expand their activities.

The researchers note that the processes accompanying the introduction of new technologies related to digitization, digital transformation and servitization become an inevitable prerequisite for changing business

models [5] or even destroying it [6] in favor of the design of new business models. Big data allows companies to make more informed decisions to increase business sustainability [7]. In addition to significant technological restructuring, business models should take into account the emergence of new forms of competition, changing values in modern society, especially after the pandemic, as well as the need to reduce carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere and increase consumer confidence [8]. Companies should focus on the formation of open business models [9] on digital platforms that take into account open innovations [10] – it is these models that maintain competitiveness based on the design of digital cooperation networks for the production of personalized products for customers and allow them to adapt to changes in the business environment and the inevitable transformation in public administration. In general, companies need to change business models in order to at least survive the digital revolution and achieve technological leadership as much as possible.

The understanding of technological leadership for the company's development is connected with the actions of management, whose role is determined by the directions of digital business transformation [11]. On the one hand, the use of digital technologies can lead to disruptions in the functioning of the business during testing periods, but, nevertheless, it provides updated opportunities for effective competition in developed and new markets.

If we consider the architecture of the business model of a modern company in the context of achieving technological leadership, then this architecture should undoubtedly include the integration of the following components:

- technical architecture,
- social architecture,
- financial architecture;
- architecture of responsibility.

Technical architecture is important for an industrial company at the factory level, it includes the technological stack of using the basic technologies of the 4th industrial revolution – 3D printing, integration of ICT systems, internet of things for manufacturing, cloud computing, Big Data, artificial intelligence in the processes and production technologies of cyber-physical systems (CPS), also known as Smart Manufacturing, Smart Factory or Manufacturing 4.0. Nevertheless, for a company in the service sector, the production architecture will mean a set of technologies that it uses to conduct business, and these will also be mainly digital and information and communication technologies. This approach proved to be convincingly proven during the pandemic, when it was companies that, with the help of the development of these technologies, preserved and multiplied their competitive advantages in difficult business conditions.

Social architecture includes all resources that are related to the human potential of the company and the competencies of employees, including unique knowledge, talent and experience. Taking into account the aspects of the use of digital technologies and a creative approach in the implementation of projects, companies create working conditions for its employees for technological leadership, not only taking into account the current organizational culture, but also taking into account the organization of various forms of employment – again, the pandemic has shown how effective remote work can be. For example, the well-known classical problem of resistance to change and something new in such companies is solved through the work of teams based on the principles of Agile project management.

The financial architecture in the company's business model for technological leadership should provide both the basic processes of current financing, as well as attracting investments and financing capital expenditures. But it is important to note here that FinTech has significantly expanded the functionality of financial management, so different forms of settlements with customers and business partners should be taken into account. Depending on the legal jurisdiction of doing business or the company's residence, there are opportunities for embedding new forms of settlements using cryptocurrencies and using digital assets in the operation of the blockchain into the business model.

The architecture of responsibility is an original part of the company's business model for technology leadership. Along with the basic corporate social responsibility, there should be an ESG-trajectory of development and energy efficiency in conjunction with digital responsibility for the use of data and ensuring its own information security. The adoption of embedding robots and devices with artificial intelligence into production processes, real-time decision-making capabilities with full electronic traceability significantly expands the functionality of business processes, which is why there is such a significant addition in the modern business environment.

Thus, the business model of technological leadership is presented not so much as a model of creating value for the client in the form of personalized products [12], but as an architecture for ensuring competitive advantages in business related to the development of production technologies and the functioning of companies in modern business conditions.

Current technological leadership business models in global markets expand the boundaries of existing business models [13] and include ecosystem-type business models that are based on the basic principles of business ecosystems. In fact, this is how a network partnership is created on a structured digital platform, which allows you to implement a lot of business ideas and expand the potential for creating value for customers and increasing business profitability for both network participants and the entire ecosystem as a whole.

However, the influence of digital transformation has determined the property of modern ecosystems as technologically complex and stable systems of interaction between participants, the basis of which is not only trust [14], dynamic cooperation and partnership [15], but also technological compatibility and integration for the purposes of ecosystem functioning. The main advantage of the ecosystem for technological leadership is the unification and even sharing of assets and technologies based on the search for innovative forms of cooperation with all business partners throughout the value chain [16]. Consequently, it is possible to strengthen the foundation of technological leadership through the exchange of ideas and knowledge, generating profits and following the principles of responsibility in doing business.

Thus, in addition to the traditional presentation of a business model as a template for defining three elements (creating business value, value proposition for creating competitive advantages and obtaining value from consumers), it is necessary to distinguish the technological leadership business models that have a certain architecture and prove the inviolability of the relationship between technology and business companies. It is this format of the business model that will allow us to realize the trajectory of the company's movement towards technological leadership in both national and global markets, taking into account market turbulence.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the authors see a certain scientific problem in the absence of a scientifically based and empirically confirmed holistic set of approaches, methods and practical recommendations for overcoming problems on the way to achieving technological leadership in areas implemented primarily in the emerging (in developing countries) and actively transforming (in developed countries) digital environment. Such a holistic complex should be built in the interaction of companies, the state and society, taking into account the need to form digital trust systems. This is especially important for companies from developing countries that can realize the real potential of development in the global spheres of production and provision of services thanks to the digital transformation of society.

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